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RESEARCHER: DR MAURIZIO SIBILLA

SUPERVISOR: DR ESRA KURUL

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TRANS-DISCIPLINARY APPROACH IN ENERGY RETROFIT: STATE OF THE ART.

1 Introduction

This study explores the concept of Energy Retrofit (ER) with particular regard to its role within the Low Carbon Transition (LCT). ER is widely recognised as relevant strategy for Low Carbon City (LCC) (Kerr, Gouldson and Barrett, 2017), and this relevance is connected with the amount of existing building stock, which has a significant incidence in European countries (Martínez-Molina *et al.*, 2016). Precisely, the European buildings that will be occupied by 2050 up to 80% have already been built (King, 2010). For this reason, ER is one of the pillars of action of the 2020 European energy strategy, (Oró *et al.*, 2015; Kylili, Fokaides and Lopez Jimenez, 2016). In detail, the European Energy Policies (i.e., the SET- Plan provisions) seek to refurbish at least 50% of existing public buildings and the retrofitting of 50% of all existing buildings in order to achieve sustainability in the built environment (Kylili, Fokaides and Lopez Jimenez, 2016; Martínez-Molina *et al.*, 2016). In such scenario, as recently underlined by (Lu *et al.*, 2017), local governs, citizens, practitioners, as well as, the building and construction industry have been called to renovate their own contribute to reducing CO2 emission and energy dependency on fossil fuels. This approach deeply involves the ER concept.

Traditionally, ER is defined as the modification of existing equipment, systems, or buildings to incorporate improved performance (ASHRAE TC 1.6, 2016). As suggested by (Webb, 2017), the typical retrofit actions concern the building components and/or building system interaction. These actions are relevant strategies for retrofitting, but they mainly focus on the technical aspects, often neglecting the social and environmental implications. The theory of the systems describe this approach as a reduction of complexity (Delattre, 1984). In the first instance, the system has less components and so, it appears easier to manage. Then, the consequence of this reduction of complexity is that the levels of uncertainties are numerous. As underlined by (Ma *et al.*, 2012) these uncertainties directly affect the selection of retrofit technologies and hence the success of a retrofit project. For example, some (Menezes *et al.*, 2012; De Wilde, 2014; Mohareb *et al.*, 2017), have pointed out the issue of the *performance gap* as result of actions developed within a system rich of uncertainties. De Wilde et al. (2014) refer to the *performance gap* as the difference between predicted energy performance of buildings and actual measured energy use once buildings are operational, quantifying in 2.5 times the predicted energy use. Menezes et al. (2012) underline how the *performance gap* erodes the credibility of the design and engineering sectors of the building industry, while Mohareb et al. (2017) point out how the *performance gap* leads to general public scepticism of new High Performance Building concepts.

Furthermore, in literature such *performance gap* is also related to the building industry fragmentation, which involves a large number of actors. Here, as highlighted by (De Wilde, 2014), the diversity of backgrounds, knowledge, position, objectives and interests means that those involved often have differing perspectives on the goals that need to be achieved and how to achieve them. So, while some studies have investigated how these diversities are key influences on construction innovation (Pinder,

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Iii and Saker, 2013; Tuohy and Murphy, 2015; Imam, Coley and Walker, 2016) others have explored the need of a progressive integration among technical and no-technical issues as driving factors in order to reduce the uncertainties of ER actions (Salter and Gann, 2003; Whyte *et al.*, 2003; Butera, 2013; Cole and Fedoruk, 2015). In addition, as demonstrated by recent works (Lu *et al.*, 2017; Soares *et al.*, 2017; Webb, 2017) an integrated investigation on ER, which is able to involve more disciplines and subjects, is always more frequently considered as the key factor to improve the success of ER projects.

Nevertheless, the ambitious goal of reducing building GHG emissions by 80% by 2050 (European Commission, 2011), as well as, the ER concepts remain challenging because of fragmented solutions that emphasize only a single driving factor continue to be the common practice. This because, working within the complexity, and hence without reductions, need to reframe the way building projects are conceptualized and implemented (Kaatz, Root and Bowen, 2005; Loftness *et al.*, 2009). However, dedicated methods in order to reframe the ER under a more inclusive approach are not sufficiently investigated. Besides, specific tools in order to improve a common language for ER and so, an appropriate knowledge exchange do not exist.

Thus, embracing the vision in which ER will play a fundamental role within the LCT, the research question is: to what extend ER can be conceptualized and implemented in order to reduce the level of uncertainties in which to operate? In order to answer this question, this work seeks to develop a novel conceptual framework with the aim at reinforcing the paradigm of transdisciplinary in ER. Specifically, it pursues: i) investigate on what constitute current research on transdisciplinary ER topics: ii) explore trends for setting the research agenda for future ER research: iii) discuss the main feature for developing a specific tools in order to improve knowledge exchange in ER. A literature review, which is focused on the restricted topic on transdisciplinary (i.e., multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary approach) in ER, is the starting point.

The structure of the paper is as follow. Section 2 analyses the existing literature reviews, pointing out the difference with this study. Section 3 describes the methodological approach adopted. Section 4 shows the main results of the literature review, proposing and analysing the main categories and lines of research on transdisciplinary in ER. Then, a novel conceptual framework is proposed. Next, Section 5, the conceptual framework is discussed in order to reinforce its role as tool to improve knowledge exchange. In addition, the future role of this conceptual framework as first step to improve a transdisciplinary ER cognitive learning platform is also presented.

2 Relevant prior literature reviews

This section introduces the literature reviews previously published in which both multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary ER topics emerge as relevant factors. The examination of the prior works has point out the richness of point of views involved on the ER topic.

For example, several works have provided a better understanding about how to conduct a building retrofit to promote energy conservation and sustainability. (Ma *et al.*, 2012) have emphasized how a wide range of retrofit technologies readily available, but methods to identify the most cost-effective retrofit measures for particular projects are still a major technical challenge. (Yushchenko and Patel, 2017) have explored the connection among different methods to assess the energy and environmental performance of buildings (i.e., life-cycle assessment methodologies, generative design methods and

retrofitting tools). (Jagarajan *et al.*, 2017) have analysed the new role of facilities management as tool to raise the proficiency and sustainability of the management of space and other related resources.

Others pursue to develop holistic approach, in particular with the support of energy modelling. For example, (Volk, Stengel and Schultmann, 2014) have promoted the dissemination of Building Information Modelling (BIM) as tool to manage the complex issues related to the existing buildings and not only for new buildings. Specifically, this study has investigated on one of the most important problem in an energy modelling of existing buildings, such as, the level of uncertain data. Instead, (Lu *et al.*, 2017) have examined BIM processes as a solution to facilitate the integration and management of information throughout the building life cycle, underling the benefit of such system in order to reduce the gaps between industry development and academic research. In particular, on the topic of life cycle approach, (Vilches, Garcia-Martinez and Sanchez-Montañes, 2017) have survived both life cycle assessment and life cycle energy analysis in order to determine which methodology is more accurate for decision making in the case of retrofitting.

At the same time, several researches have focused on the new technology systems, which are deeply modifying the approach of the urban transformations. For example, (Allegrini *et al.*, 2015) have proposed a review of modelling approaches and tools for the simulation of district-scale energy systems. In this work the interactions between ER and urban retrofit emerge. In such scenario, the recent advances in information and communications technology have acquired more and more importance. So, a new topic has emerged, as underlined by (Lawrence *et al.*, 2016), which have explored the range of complex issues and topics associated with using emerging technologies for integrating buildings and their systems into a smart grid. Moreover, the issue of the smart grid has enhanced the interest in energy storage systems located very close to consumers, which has opened, as stressed by (Parra *et al.*, 2017), an interdisciplinary investigation on the role of community energy storage as a key element within the wider renewable energy system..

To put at the centre of the interests the citizens and their communities within the LCT is another topic which is becoming increasingly important and it is modifying the ER approach. This investigation is developed on different level. For example, (Camprubí *et al.*, 2016) has investigated on the technical aspect of façade insulation related to the implication political and social contexts. The scope of this study is to better understand the mechanisms that explain how and why variations across different social groups appear in receiving energy efficiency façade retrofitting interventions and in their impact on health determinants. The social role of ER action emerges also in other recent works. For example, (Martínez-Molina *et al.*, 2016) have proposed a literature review on methods and strategies used in order to maintain built heritage values of historic buildings, while achieving significant improvements in their energy efficiency. On the same topic, (Webb, 2017) have pointed how the issue of energy efficiency in historic building have informed local regulatory policies. Additionally, as concern the local level, (Olubunmi, Xia and Skitmore, 2016) have explored how the financial and non-financial incentives are important tools to develop local ER strategies and how this tools involve the different actors of local communities (i.e. owner, tenants, government, etc..).

Last but not the least, there are several works which have focused on the LCT phases. These works have emphasized the need to develop a new energy management strategies in order to aid the researchers and decision makers in applying the procedures (Bhowmik *et al.*, 2017), as well as, to guide a deep renovation of building sector (Wang *et al.*, 2017). In particular, (Wang *et al.*, 2017), have proposed a new framework to guide potential evolution of the building stock in the next century,

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based on greenhouse gas emissions as the common thread to investigate the potential implications of new design paradigms, innovative operational strategies, and disruptive technologies. This framework emphasizes integration of multidisciplinary knowledge, and proactive approaches considering constraints and unknowns.

Therefore, what emerges from the state of art is that the multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary approaches are both considered as key factors to better understand the complex dynamic about the interactions between the ER and the built environment. All prior literature reviews scrutinized constitute a relevant contribute in order to understand and manage the ER complexity. Nevertheless, these works have investigated within pre-defined interactions (i.e., innovation technology and social change, or energy modelling and life cycle assessment, or ER solution and cultural heritage). Consequently, an ER conceptual framework, which works at a higher level of complexity, is needed, as first step in order to: 1) better understand the future ER lines of research, operating within an increasing level of complexity; 2) develop innovative human capabilities, improving the ability to exploit external knowledge; 3) design technological solutions for deep ER.

3 Research methods

This work is based on a literature review, which is pertinent approach in order to identify the existing body on knowledge and point out potential research gap (Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003). Specifically, in this work a literature review is used as first step of a broader investigation, which seeks to build an innovative cognitive learning platform based on transdisciplinary in ER. Therefore, the whole project will be developed in several steps. Specifically, three steps are fundamental: the first step in which the investigation moves from a literature review to a conceptual framework; the second, in which the conceptual framework will be transformed in a cognitive learning platform, the third, where the platform will be tested in empirical learning experiences for practitioners, researchers and students. The first step is the argument of this paper. It is essential step in order to capture the level of transdisciplinary, which is currently characterizing the research and the relevant experiences and so, giving back a unitary conceptual framework. Taking into account the final objective of the research (i.e., the cognitive learning platform), a mix of systematic process of qualitative and quantitative contents analyses were used. The final products of qualitative and quantitative approach are different. Nevertheless, the two approaches are not mutually exclusive and can be used in combination (Zhang and Wildemuth, 2009). So, firstly, this work opted for qualitative approach, as defined by (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005) as a research method for the subjective interpretation of the content of text data through the systematic classification process of coding and identifying themes or patterns. Secondly, the methodological approach was integrated with a quantitative approach as described by (Zhang and Wildemuth, 2009) as data are selected using random sampling or other probabilistic approaches, so as to ensure the validity of statistical inference (i.e., frequency word analysis). The qualitative approach was used in order to provide a novel conceptual framework on transdisciplinary ER approach. The quantitative approach was applied in order to collect relevant concepts, which are the basis for developing a cognitive transdisciplinary ER Learning Platform.

The systematic process of content analysis was developed, adapting and integrating the phases described by (May *et al.*, 2016) which refer to some prior works, in particular (Mayring, 2000, 2008). Specifically, the integrations refer to the cognitive mapping methodology (Novak and Cañas, 2004; Cañas and Novak, 2008; Novak, 2011). The phases are described below:

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- Phase 1: focalization of the research domain. Selection of pertinent literature.
- Phase 2: coding unit. Identification of relevant themes or patterns, assessing contribute of each reference.
- Phase 3: category definition. Grouping relevant information under main categories (or sub-categories is needed) in order to reveal the level of transdisciplinary work in progress.
- Phase 4: word-frequency analysis. Collecting relevant concepts and their distribution among the categories as nodes of further interaction levels.
- Phase 5: conceptual framework definition. Definition of the categories (and sub-categories), paving the way to a clear future perspective.

The publications were searched on University Library Data Base, which include all relevant scientific collections (e.g., Emerald-insight, Sage, Scopus, Springer, Taylor & Francis and others). This literature review has taken into account only journal papers published in English in order to increase the feasibility to compare the research works. Figure 1 shows the evolution of the database search. This study focused on papers published in the last 20 years (i.e., 1997 until 2017). ER search term yielded 12.157 papers. Following an advanced search strategy and in coherence with the research objective, a Boolean keyword search was chosen to include relevant key-words such as *Multidisciplinary* and *Interdisciplinary*.

Figure 1. Search process

Precisely, this study refers to the definition of *multidisciplinary* (i.e., the subject under study is approached from different angles, using different disciplinary perspectives) and *interdisciplinary* (the approach creates its own theoretical, conceptual and methodological identity to study of a certain problem) described in (Van Den Besselaar and Heimeriks, 2001). Currently, both these approaches are important, because they represent the efforts to reduce the *performance gap* and the fragmentation. In particular, in order to capture the most relevant contribute, this study refers to the

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integrated approach as *transdisciplinary* with the aim to take into account both multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary methodologies, which involve the most advanced works on urban and building ER.

After this restriction, 585 papers remained. Subsequently, after obtaining this set of papers, a set of criteria were established in order to identify the relevant papers which were directly relevant for the research question. Two inclusion criteria were established:

- Research papers where the ER concept was applied to the field of building and urban transformation (e.g. papers that focus on ER in mechanical engineering or chemical processes were excluded)
- Research papers where a Multidisciplinary or Interdisciplinary approach was confirmed through a preliminary assessment of title, keywords and abstract.

Additionally, two exclusion criteria were adopted:

- Research papers that focused on literature review, conceptual framework or state of the art (which were used to give evidence of the originality of this literature review).
- Research papers mainly focused on specific technical application (which will be used in the second step of the research, in order to improve the technical information within the learning platform).

Using the criteria explained above, 136 relevant papers on transdisciplinary in ER were identified as subjects of this literature review.

Then, the papers were read and analysed with the support of Nvivo in order to develop a coding process of relevant information (Phase 2). Next, the papers were analysed using the inductive method in order to build the categories (Phase 3). Here, in agreement with May et al, (2017) the inductive method was considered more appropriate than the deductive methods. Thus, in this case, the scope of the research was to point out what are the emerging issues related to the ER.

Of course, during the coding process numerous overlaps among the papers were observed. In order to reduce the frequency of overlaps, each paper was categorised according to its particular point of view or focus in the field. By doing so, each paper has contributed to the identification and development of specific topic. After collecting a multitude of information on specific topic, the category was defined. There is no a specific rule on how much information the identification and development of a specific topic. Nevertheless, it was deemed reasonable to integrate at least three different points of view on the same topic, in order to define a transdisciplinary category. In this sense, each journal paper was considered as a representative of a specific point of view in terms of thinking, method or tool.

The categories were organized according to prioritized themes, patterns and concepts. This approach refers to cognitive mapping methodology (Novak and Cañas, 2004) and it has permitted the establishment of significant relationships within the reviewed body of literature. At the same time, new connections or order could always be introduced. Within a category, the wealth of information on a specific topic has determined the definition of sub-categories. Here, the sub-categories were called *lines of research* because they point out a current relevant theme about transdisciplinary ER investigation.

A set of main concepts were associate to the categories and the lines of research In Phase 4. The concepts were selected with the support of word frequency analysis in Nvivo. This analysis was

applied both at the categories and the lines of research. The concepts were collected following this procedure:

- Firstly, the word frequency criteria were defined. The analysis considers the 25 most frequent words, with a minimum length of 3 letters and grouping with synonymous (e.g., planning, design, programme and project).
- Secondly, in order to enhance the wealth of nodes (and therefore a wealth of meaningful transdisciplinary relationships, each word was associated to a single category (or line of research). The word frequency analysis defines the hierarchical order of each word within a category. Consequently, the distribution of the word was a fast procedure. Nevertheless, in some limited case, in which the number of frequency for a word appears the same for both categories, the procedure suggests to pass a qualitative assessment (i.e., using text search analysis) in which the contexts of the word were showed in word tree representation. So, the most relevant patten detected for the word analysed has determined its category.
- Thirdly, all trial words which were not expression of concept were not taken into account (e.g., date, total, results, however and others).

By doing so, the list of relevant concepts becomes the starting node to connect the information belonging to different categories and lines of research. This is will be part of the next phase of the investigation.

Finally (Phase 5), the assessment of the results (themes, patterns) with a novel integration of relevant concepts was carried out in form of a new conceptual framework on transdisciplinary in ER.

4 Results

This section illustrates the results of the research. A brief review of the descriptive results introduces this section in order to provide evidence of the broad spectrum of arguments involved. Table 1 shows the distribution of the papers across journal. The table supports the understanding to assess how the topic was widely approached within the research community. Instead, in term of time distribution the papers collected mainly refer to the last 5 years (respect to the whole range of selection from 1997-2017), confirming an increasing interest by the scientific community on the multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary ER approach.

The central part of this section focuses on the results of the content analyses. The figure 2 shows the conceptual framework on the transdisciplinary in ER, which represents the main result of this examination. The conceptual framework is composed by 5 categories; 15 lines of research (three of each category); 50 relevant concepts. It provides an answer on what constitute current research on the transdisciplinary topic. In addition, the conceptual framework includes relevant research themes in ER, exploring trends for setting the research agenda for future research. Section 4.1 (i.e., content analysis) delivers the critical description about the categories and the lines of research, classifying the transdisciplinary scopes pointed out by the paper analysed.

Up 4 papers		From 1 to 4 papers (total 39 papers):	
Energy and Buildings	39	Automation in Construction,1	Journal of Cultural Heritage,1
Energy policy	11	Advances in Building Energy Research,1	Journal of Industrial Ecology,1
Building Research and Information	10	Applied Thermal Engineering,1	Journal of Urban Technology,1
Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews	8	Architectural Science Review,1	Journal of Planning Education and Research,1
Energy	7	Building Research and Information Buildings,2	Land Use Policy,1
Applied Energy	6	Canadian Journal of Civil Engineering,1	Management of Environmental Quality,1
Building and Environment	6	Computers in Industry,1	Philosophical transactions. Series A Mathematical,1
Journal of Cleaner Production	5	Construction and Building Materials,1	Progress in Human Geography,1
Sustainable Cities and Society	5	Construction Innovation,1	Renewable Energy,1
		Energies,2	Research Policy,1
		Energy Conversion and Management,2	Solar Energy,2
		Environment and Planning D: Society and Space,1	Structural Survey,1
		Environmental Science and Policy,1	Technological Forecasting & Social Change,1
		Expert Systems With Applications,1	The Historic Environment: Policy & Practice,1
		Geoforum,1	Urban Design International,1
		Indoor and Built Environment,1	Urban Research and Practice,1
		Journal of Building Physics,3	

Table 1. Distribution across main journals

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework

4.1 Content analysis

In the following sections the description of the categories and the lines of research are provided.

4.1.1 ER and low carbon city transition.

The works belonging to this category show some relevant relationships between the ER actions and the low carbon transition. Urban (i.e., as urban context) is the key concept in which deep renovations emerge. Such renovations concern both technical and no technical strategies which involve the traditional ER concept. The following lines of researches describe the high level of transdisciplinary interactions collected with these works. The references are organized in the table 2.

(Table 2. ER and low carbon city transition category and lines of research-attached)

From Building Retrofit to Urban Retrofit.

The documents categorized in this line of research support a fundamental step from ER, as tool to improve building performance, towards Urban Retrofit, as set of strategies to improve adaptation capacity of the local settlements to address global **climate** concern. This approach seeks to reduce the risks of fragmentation, which a practice often seen in single building level. Therefore, at city level, as well as, at a neighbourhood scale is required much more coordinated, planned and strategic approach in order to improve energy **performance** at large-scale energy. Urban **planning** is called to integrate topics such as economies of scale on energy savings and investment cost. At the same time, the energy issues have to face the complex stratification which composes the urbane morphology. This means that the intrinsically features of the settlements, which are often part of a cultural heritage, especially in the case of European city, have to take into account in order to contrast homogenized forms of intervention.

Technical and Social Integration.

This line of research classifies several papers in which the interactions between technical and social **innovation** in ER sector emerge. This approach switches the problems on how to disseminate a widespread technical **culture** among the actors (i.e public, private, communities, industries). What emerge from literature is that each actor could play a specific role within the low carbon transition path. Nevertheless, the synchronization among these actors, especially in a small and medium city, is very hard to obtain. Consequently, the economic analysis remains the most consolidate approach. But, in the last decade, the innovation technologies (i.e., the dissemination of information and communication technologies) seems to support an increasingly synchronization among the actors, promoting an unpublished **cultural** innovation. Consequently, cultural innovation and innovation technologies in ER are becoming the main tools to to achieve both a high level of environmental qualities and quality of life.

Disruptive and Sustainable local technologies.

The title of this line of research is replaced from Dixon, Eames, Britnell, Watson, & Hunt (2014) because it well expresses the need to work on ER disciplinary bounders rather than the reassuring

disciplinary silos. Hence, the papers collected shows how the diffusion of smart technological solutions is allowing to deepening and expanding the level of information available, but the investigation on how to use and integrate the multitude on information today represents an opened challenge. Consequently, it emerges the need to select define relevant information and appropriate sustainable local technologies. This implies, as defined by (Glackin and Dionisio, 2016), a *deep engagement* of local **communities** in order to face the **change** towards the low carbon society and so, to promote a **regeneration process** for the settlement.

4.1.2 Information modelling process.

This category comprises the studies which have developed methods and tools in order to optimize processes and products related to ER actions. Simulation is the key concept, which refers to the scope of reducing the level of uncertainties in which to work. As well known, these uncertainties undermine the environmental qualities, as well as, both the investment possibilities and urban energy policies. So, in order to contrast the level of uncertainty three transdisciplinary lines of research have been underlined. The references are organized in the table 3.

(Table 3. ER and information modelling process category and lines of research- attached)

Energy modelling process.

This line of research includes papers which have investigated on methods and tools for energy modelling processes. Specifically, how to **calibrate** such modelling process respect to the real conditions with the aim to feedback complete framework about energy **consumption**, seem to be one of the most important contemporary problem. Traditionally, the energy modelling process has been focused at the building scale, analysing mainly the building envelop and its plant systems interactions. In contrast, the most advanced experiences in ER seek to assess the available **options**, taking into account the influence between the internal and external factors of the building, the environmental impact of technological solutions on long period and the potentialities for large scale investments in energy retrofit of buildings. Nevertheless, these variables are often interpreted differently among disciplines, datasets and contexts. The improvement of these tools is ongoing.

Occupant behaviour modelling

This line of research focuses on the role of occupant **behaviour** within the modelling process and so, the **use** of representative **data**. Traditionally, in ER, energy efficiency issues are overemphasized, while other key issues, (e.g., health and comfort of occupants associated with indoor air quality and noise levels) have been less stressed and discussed. Moreover, traditional energy models rely on predictive indicators and assumptions that are usually done at the design stage, without acknowledging behavioural patterns of actual users. Recently, retrofit measures, from the point of view on how to balance energy and comfort needs, have acquired more relevance. Here, the occupant behaviour has been recognized as component of a transdisciplinary approach in order to give more detailed on a specific local context.

Life cycle analysis modelling

This line of research highlights the interaction between the life cycle approach and the ER actions in order to achieve a better forecast about the metabolism of the building The key concept is represented

by the **assessment** of life cycle **performances**, which emphasizes the importance of having meaningful building energy monitoring capabilities, an understanding of energy system boundaries in design and analysis, crossing the gaps between different stages of a building life cycle, and feedback processes throughout design and operation. The results show how embody energy is another complex factor to assess the retrofit actions which involves: construction materials and components used during retrofits, the main components of conventional and renewable energy systems, as well as, the impacts related to the building construction, for the different elements and the whole building.

4.1.3 Decision-making process

Under this category there are papers which are focused on systematic methodology and corresponding tools to support innovative ER decision-making process for the integration of various improvement options, including new technologies, urban infrastructure, as well as, energy and market policies. Multi-Optimization is the main concept, which refers to integrated procedure analysis in ER. Specifically, after analysing the articles, three relevant lines of research emerge. The references are organized in the table 4.

(Table 4. ER and decision-making process category and lines of research – Attached)

Multi-attribute information.

This line of research includes the optimization of methods and tools to gathering multi-attribute information. Traditionally the multi-attribute information in the ER field was applied in order to determine the optimal solution in terms of **financial** investment **cost**. Recently, new multi-attribute decision-making methods have been developed in in order to prioritize the alternatives of comparative projects quite accurately. Currently the multi-attribute information in the ER seek to define the local **mechanisms** which determine the optimization of the solution.

Bottom-up methodology

This line of research underlines the importance to optimize the bottom-up methodology to aid decision-makers in the energy planning process. New bottom-up methodologies seek to improve voluntary and regulatory approaches and develop new planning process for urban resilience. In such scenario, the decision policies are called: to identify the local **criteria** for successful renovation packages; to consider the local **incentives** for policies implementation; and, to identify local renovation packages that needs to be prioritized which are based on inhabitant's point of view.

Economic and socio-technical factors

This line of research seeks to enhance the economic and socio-technical factors which are involved in ER actions. An example is represented by the decision process of renewable energy systems integration at large scale. (i.e., PV energy system integration). In such context, the **economic** and socio-technical factors are deeply connected with each other. Consequently, neglecting the **integration** among economic and socio-technical factors can influence the **investments** capacity and consequently reduce the success of retrofit actions.

4.1.4 ER and innovative technical solutions

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The papers fitting to this category describe several technical innovations concerning the building envelop, the plant systems, users and their interactions. **Thermal Heat** is the main concept and this category explains how technical solutions for thermal heat involve transdisciplinary goals. Such transdisciplinary is here presented by the following lines of research. The references are organized in the table 5.

(Table 5 ER and innovative technical solutions category and lines of research Attached)

Innovative building materials

Traditionally, the energy performances of building materials are related with the thermal **properties** (e.g., transmittance, **inertia** and specific heat). These properties are used to analyse the steady-state or dynamic state in order to reveal the building energy behaviour under determined conditions. This line of research extends the interaction on a transdisciplinary investigation, which include environmental and ecological issues. These interactions concern the embody energy of retrofit actions (e.g. natural **insulation**), as well as, constructive solutions (e.g. green roofs and vertical greening systems). In particular, these constructive solutions are recognized as optimal retrofit solutions in order to improve the urban heat island mitigation strategies. Consequently, this line of research reinforces, again, the large scale of retrofit solutions, in this case, starting from a punctual technical solution.

Passive, active and smart technologies

This line of research focuses on the **integrated** strategies among passive, active and smart energy technologies in order to improve the efficiency and the quality of life. Traditionally, the internal comfort and energy performance are considered two faces of the same coin, but only recently the user's comprehension of available technologies are playing a central role. Smart advices have allowed to customizing both the passive and the active energy strategies. They allow a direct **control** on the engineering devices which are able to control **bioclimatic** parameters (i.e., solar and ventilation) in order to achieve the best solution.

Building sector renovation

As well known, the building sector plays an important role in order to reduce the environmental impact. This line of research points out the transdisciplinary addresses, which involve social, economic and environmental factors connected with a hypothesis of building sector renovation. The experiences reveal how the economic competitiveness of the building industries requires the development of systems able to capture CO₂ from the industrial process (e.g. cement industry); the development of low cost technical solutions for the intervention on existing buildings (e.g., **prefabricated** retrofit module); and, the development of a more consistence dialogue between the **industry** and **research** centers, adopting an integrated multi-objective design process.

4.1.5 Energy and environmental awareness

This category collects works which have focused their investigation on methods and tools to improve energy and environmental awareness among the actors of the urban regeneration process. The key main concept of this category is the **Knowledge**. Specifically, within this category the papers focused on the role of communities' knowledge and users' Knowledge. In addition the role of practitioners, researchers and industry sector have been examined. Three lines of research have emerged as

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representative of transdisciplinary in ER, which are below described. The references are organized in the table 6.

(Table 6. ER and energy and environmental awareness category and lines of research – attached)

Integrated Community energy system

Recently, the importance of socio-geographic places of energy transition is emerging as first factor in order to develop efficacy retrofit actions. In particular, one of the emerging topics is the multifaceted interplay between place, **local entrepreneurship** and community. Relevant is the case of the integrated community energy systems, which are emerging as a modern economic and social development to re-organize local energy systems (e.g., **decentralized** sustainable energy systems). The new energy scenario allows a simultaneous integration of distributed energy resources and engagement of local communities. The distributed energy systems requires active acceptance by inhabitants.

Comfort and Quality of life

Currently, strategies to promote behaviour changes are investigated. The results point out how the relation between comfort and quality of life can be interpreted in several ways. On the one hand, there is the context in which the smart technologies have been successful applied and integrated in ER actions in order to improve the energy building performance; on the other hand, there is the context of fuel poverty in which the problem of the consumption is secondary respects to the quality of life. In the first case, the behaviours of the final users are particular interesting in order to identify significant issues in the reliability and usability of the energy technologies. The grade of satisfaction of the final users and the confidence with smart devices are the main topics investigated. In the second case, the behaviours of the final users are relevant in order to promote energy **policy instrument** in order to move from behaviour change to systemic change. Therefore, the environmental value is combined with the **social** purpose of reducing inequalities. In this case, one of the best examples is the retrofit actions in social housing.

Socio-technological learning process

In relation to a new set of urban complex issues (i.e., urban energy transition), the knowledge transfer has acquired a new level of complexity. Specifically, in the next future citizen-centred energy systems will acquire more and more consideration, and this requires better prepared citizens on energy technological issues. Therefore, in order to face a socio-technological transition both expert and non-expert are called to expand their ability to transfer and acquire information. At the same time, the future practitioners will be called to manage material and immaterial processes with a high level of disciplinary connections. New forms of technology **education** are emerging through **experiments** which are focused on how to improve the technological knowledge of local communities (i.e., Urban Living Urban Lab). Nevertheless, there is a need to clarify what makes these new approaches attractive and novel and their role on a dissemination of ER actions as tool to socio-technological transition.

5 Discussion.

This study has explored the concept of ER with particular regard to its role related to the LCT. Thus, the main finding of this study is the feedback of a conceptual framework dedicated to the transdisciplinary in ER, currently in progress. Specifically, with regard to the research question, aforementioned conceptual framework seeks to clarify how ER can be conceptualized and implemented in order to reduce the level of uncertainties in which to operate. In detail, the 5 categories make explicit what constitute current research on the transdisciplinary ER topic (i), whereas the 15 lines of research explore trends for setting the research agenda for future ER research (ii). In this section a discussion is proposed with the aim at examining the main features introduced by the conceptual framework, and how these features are the core for improving knowledge exchange in ER (iii) whole modalities will be explored in next step of this research.

5.1 Novelties of the ER transdisciplinary conceptual framework.

As mentioned in the introduction, the conceptual framework confirms that a multitude of actors are called to change their internal organization in order to achieve a mature low carbon society. Specifically, the lines of research underline how the innovation technologies, environmental and energy qualities are factors intrinsically connected to each other, nowadays. These new connections do not involve only the technical aspects of the LCT, but they involve the whole society in a deep change. Consequently, this conceptual framework makes it clear that the ER concept is now under pressure and profound changes are required in order to improve its strategic role related to the LCT. In particular, this pressure, as showed by literature analysis, derives from the high level of fragmentation. This conceptual framework tells a story about these levels of fragmentation in ER, pointing out new forms of organization to contrast them.

The first fragmentation level is related to the unclear role of the ER actions within the LCT. ER actions are mostly confined within disciplinary silos, as well as, the most advanced integrated experiences are relegated to experimental projects. In contrast, the first category of the conceptual framework (i.e., Low carbon city transition) clarifies *what is changing*. The conceptual framework shows how a new comprehensive approach is needed and ER at large scale is ever more considered the appropriate level of observation for exploring the obstacles that impede cities from addressing global climate concerns, the opportunities for removing the obstacles, and strategies for bringing global issues onto the local level. In particular, the lines of research show how the most advanced experiences of ER actions consider the built environment as a social–ecological system, in which ER is a strategy to develop the adaptation capacity of the local community, promoting a technical and cultural innovation. In this context, the disruptive and sustainable local technologies are those are working to promote regeneration processes of the settlements, emphasizing the need of a more proactive orientation, and coordination among diverse actors and industry groups.

The second level of fragmentation concerns the use of advanced tools. On the one hand, the research is developing sophisticated algorithms and procedures in order to collect and analyse relevant data. On the other hand, the multitude of data is generating a large amount of specialized language. Consequently, in the common practices it is more and more difficult recognize and prioritize relevant information. In contrast, the second category of the conceptual framework (i.e., Information modelling process) suggest us *what we need*. The conceptual framework shows how the emerging technologies of energy informatics support us in the process to expand the energy modelling process

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towards the large scale The access to this data permits us to capture both individual building characteristics and trends within a neighbourhood. The results of literature review exalt the role of this factor, proposing a new set of methodologies in order to develop a more accurate integrated evaluation system. Therefore, the ability to define forecast both in the short and long term is a requisite we need in order to optimize the environment and financial cost of the ER solutions. and integrated them into the LCT.

The third fragmentation level regards the dissemination of procedures which are able to integrated different point of view. Whereas we have implemented the tools to gathering information, the skills to transfer them in the context of the urban transformation require managerial abilities often neglected. In contrast, the third category of the conceptual framework (i.e., Decision making process) explains *how we manage*. The conceptual framework points out how the multi-attribute information approach seeks to a network synergy effect, taking into account financial, human and technical local resources, with the aim at pointing out the local mechanism has to be put in place in order to achieve the optimal solution. The lines of research show how to analyse the inhabitant's point of view and their participation, becomes a relevant factor in order to disseminate appropriate ER solution. Consequently, the results show how the new approaches seek to improve the skills of the local community to understand the value of the local resources, as well as, to understand the investments and the benefit of ER actions.

The forth level of fragmentation involves the use of technical innovations. The literature has showed how the balances between the energy and environmental qualities are often contradictory issues. Consequently, the forth category (i.e., Innovative technical solutions) expresses *what we implement*. Specifically, the lines of research pursue to enhance the energy performances and the ecological qualities interactions. Therefore, the findings show how the most advanced experiences about ER actions are improving, on the one side, the efficiency of the systems (i.e., the integration of smart energy systems as micro grids, smart buildings, smart advices); on the other side, the enhancement of environmental approaches to preserve the features of the buildings and settlements. Moreover, an integrated approach which seeks to reduce the environmental impact of the building industry processes is considered as fundamental component in order to achieve a new form of economic competitiveness.

The fifth level of fragmentation concern the form of knowledge which involves technicians, non-technician and institutions. This type of fragmentation is due to the lack of resilience of the old apparatus in which to transfer the outputs of experimental actions into common practices. Currently, this transfer is often impracticable, because of the resistances of the communities, the inappropriateness of policies and the lack of dialogue among disciplines and sectors. In contrast, the fifth category (i.e., Energy and environmental awareness) emphasizes *which are the outputs*. Therefore, this category closes the circle. It states how ER actions, need of a new apparatus, which involve a new set of organization rules and new knowledges for the actors involved in LTC. This unpublished collaboration seeks to define, as indicated by (Zeleny, 1986, 2012), a technology support network. Technology Support Net consists of work rules, task rules, requisite skills, work content, standards and measures, styles, culture and organizational patterns (Zeleny, 2012). It has to be developed *in situ* and Knowledge has to be produced within the specific local context (Zeleny, 2009).

Consequently, each category, as well as, each line of research provides an address to contrasting both managerial deficiency and technical inability to work together within the complexity of the built

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environment. The conceptual framework proposed makes evidence how the investigation on ER mainly requires a *change of scale*. With the term of *change of scale* this study refers to those experiences which have investigated on a new dimension of the relationships about ER actions. Therefore, the conceptual framework, respect to the past study, offers an organized vision of this new dimension of the relationships about ER actions, exploring the components involved and clarifying the key elements of the process.

5.2 Limitations and future research

The *change of scale* in ER is undoubtedly related, as repeatedly stressed, to a new energy infrastructure paradigm, as more resilient and ecologic system to support the LCT. The results of the literature review have emphasized the interactions among ER actions and the emerging technologies, such as the decentralized sustainable energy systems. Nevertheless, the results clearly show how the success of the dissemination at local level of this new energy paradigm is mainly related with the development of new organized system which involves researchers, practitioners, industries, governance and citizens as parts of a Technology Support Net, rather than a sectorial engineering vision of the problem (see section 2). Specifically, before, ER focused on how to improve building performances in order to reduce the global carbon emission of the building sectors. Now, ER includes a complex set of strategies to achieve a mature low carbon society.

By doing so, this transdisciplinary investigation on ER has pointed out how several typologies of *performance gap* exist, which obstacle the path toward a mature low carbon society. Consequently, the ER issue related to the *performance gap* has acquired a new perspective. In detail, this work sustains that in order to contrast the levels of fragmentation, it is better to refer to a *knowledge gap*. So, while the *performance gap* measures the asynchrony between the performances of building through the different stage of its life, the *knowledge gap* measures the local actors' ability to manage ER actions within the local complexity of the low carbon transition. In other word, the *knowledge gap* measures the local capacity to organize a technology support network.

From this point of view, a consideration about the usefulness of the conceptual framework emerges. This concern moves from an investigation process which works to expand the categories and the lines of research, towards a process which seeks to support the knowledge transfer within the network. Thus, the conceptual framework, as proposed, is the starting point because it has truly an important role in order to stimulate an inclusive debate. In addition, it is a good tool to create access to interdisciplinary knowledge for the network actors involved in ER. Nevertheless, this access is a necessary, but not sufficient condition to lead to knowledge transfer. Consequently, in order to enhance the knowledge transfer within the network, the conceptual framework is called to support the development of new cognitive abilities.

(Cohen and Levinthal, 1990) call these abilities as absorptive capacity. The absorptive capacity implies to recognize the value of new, external information, assimilate it, and apply it. The ability to exploit external knowledge is thus a critical component of innovative capabilities (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990). In all reference analysed in this literature review there is a strong stress of this issue in order to enhance the interactions among disciplines. Nevertheless, there are few studies that examine how improve the networks affect, the organization's ability to acquire new knowledge from the network and facilitate the transfer of knowledge among network members. As pointed out by (Inkpen and Tsang, 2005, 2011; Hosseini and Akhavan, 2015) the theme of knowledge transfer within

the network is essential for its operation. Consequently, we need to develop a tool which can support us to move from a hierarchical organization of the complex topics towards a network of knowledge transfer (Figure 3).

Figure 3. From a hierarchy model of the knowledge towards a network of knowledge transfer

Thus, which is the challenge for the next future? As noted by Altomonte (2009) (Torres-Ramírez *et al.*, 2014; Ismail, Keumala and Dabdoob, 2017), future professionals are required to be more equipped with advanced technical skills in order to deliver sustainability. Moreover, as very recently underlined by (Adams, Martin and Boom, 2018) the sustainability integration in higher education need to be better understand. Higher education is called to train a new generation of practitioners (i.e., as actors of the network) who should be able to manage technical and social changes about sustainability. In addition, future researchers and practitioners interested in LCT could play a relevant role in order to organize the technology support network of such sustainability. Hence, the new question is: how to transform the conceptual framework in a tool to organize a technology support network. How to improve the absorptive capacity of the future researcher and practitioners? A combined use of cognitive approach and meaningful learning activities in order to move from conceptual framework to a cognitive interdisciplinary learning platform is a possible solution. This aspect will be explored in the next phase of this research.

6 Conclusion

Despite in literature the need to move towards a more inclusive approach is recognized as relevant topic, the fragmentation among disciplines is a significant problem yet. This study have developed a literature review which has involved 136 journal papers, in order to feedback a conceptual framework on the level of multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary approaches currently adopted in the field of urban and building ER. Thus, 5 categories, 15 lines of research and 50 main concepts have been classified and discussed in order to better understand the role of the ER within the path towards a mature low carbon society. Specifically, the conceptual framework clarifies the components involved within the transition towards a decentralized sustainable energy system. Here, the *change of scale* about the ER topic has been underlined has an emerging topic, which suggest to reinforce a transdisciplinary investigation on ER. Following this view, the actors involved in the ER actions will be called to improve their ability to manage the knowledge transfer. Consequently, this study has

argued how to solve the *Knowledge gap* among the actors is emerging as a mainly issue in order to improve an appropriate Technology Support Net, which will be called to improve the retrofit actions at large scale for LCT. Finally, the paper has proposed a new direction of investigation, which moves from the conceptual framework towards an innovative learning platform in order to provide a new tool to train the next generation of researchers and practitioners, as a member of the Technology Support Net, to better understand how to work together within the complexity of the built environment.

Category: ER and low carbon city transition – main key concept: URBAN

Line of Research	References	Transdisciplinary scope detected:	Key Concepts
From Building Retrofit R to Urban Retrofit	(Cajot <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	The paper aims to make clear the many interrelated challenges and obstacles which hinder efficient urban energy planning.	Planning Performance Climate
	(Gregório and Seixas, 2017)	The paper supports the a holistic approach at a neighbourhood scale, instead of the traditional individual building scale	
	(Becchio <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	The paper analyses the new emerging concept of “Post-Carbon City” and its main influencing factors regarding the building sector.	
	(Wu, Wang and Xia, 2016)	The paper analyses the large-scale Building energy efficiency retrofit	
	(Magrini and Franco, 2016)	The paper investigates on the relationships between ER issues and cultural heritage ones as high level of complexity the society is called to face.	
	(Gupta <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	The paper investigates on retrofit programmes in order to reduce the gap between intent and outcome.	
	(Mazzarella, 2015)	The paper investigates on the gap between historic building and energy retrofit.	
	(Jennings, Fisk and Shah, 2014)	The paper examines the retrofit problems at urban scale providing solutions for the selection and operation of complex energy systems.	
	(Dixon and Eames, 2013)	The paper investigates on mitigation and adaptation responses to climate change along with the allied threats of environmental degradation.	
	(Mehaffy, 2013)	The paper studies the variables of urban morphology and their role in the generation of greenhouse gas emissions.	
Technical and Social Integration.	(Bai, 2007)	This article explores the obstacles that impede cities from addressing global environmental concerns.	Environment Innovation Culture
	(Gianfrate <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	The paper focuses on the relationship between technological advancements and knowledge in energy retrofiting with social needs and habits.	
	(van Krugten <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	The paper addresses the knowledge gap of the current energy performance of historical dwellings.	
	(Broto, 2015)	The paper presents an analysis of contradictions in urban low carbon transitions as engines of change.	
	(Cosmi <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	The paper proposes a holistic approach in order to enhance the energy systems in terms of policy background, energy uses and infrastructures.	
	(Dall’O’ <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	The paper proposes a methodology that integrates multi-criteria analysis in order to support Public Administration/Local Authorities in programming Action Plans	
	(Head, 2010)	The paper points out the role of Adaptation as a core concept of twentieth-century cultural ecology.	
	(Kelly, 2010)	The paper investigates on the engineering challenge associated with energy security, climate change and sustainable consumption of existing buildings.	
Disruptive and Sustainable local technologies	(Smith, Voß and Grin, 2010)	The paper focuses on the multi-level perspective of socio-technical transitions.	Change Community Regeneration
	(Moffatt and Kohler, 2008)	The paper proposes a unified theory of the built environment as a complex social-ecological system, where multiple-related metabolisms interact at different scales	
	(Fonseca <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	The paper describes a computational framework for the analysis and optimization of energy systems in neighbourhoods and city districts.	
	(Glackin and Dionisio, 2016)	The paper focuses a new methodology for community engagement in the urban regeneration process introducing the so called: ‘deep engagement’.	
	(Dixon <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	The paper investigates on the importance to identify ‘disruptive’ and ‘sustaining’ technologies which may contribute to city-based sustainability transitions	
	(Eames <i>et al.</i> ,	The paper explores the complex urban transitions under a multiple socio-technical	

2013)	'regimes', scales and domains within a participatory process.
(Mills, 2003)	The paper proposes an integration of sustainable energy considerations with risk-management objectives, underlining a more proactive coordination among groups.

Table 2. Low carbon city transition category and lines of research

Category: ER and information modelling process – main concept: SIMULATION			
Line of Research	References	Trans-disciplinary scope detected:	Key Concepts
Energy modelling process	(Cao <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	The paper presents an automatic geometry modelling procedure of existing building facades in order to recover their semantic structure for reuse in the BEM process.	Calibration Consumption Options
	(Heidarinejad <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	The paper presents a procedure to rapidly create urban scale reduced order building energy models	
	(Wu <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	The paper illustrates a method for a multi-objective and simultaneous optimisation of building energy systems and retrofit	
	(Alwan, 2016)	The paper presents a systematic framework for maintenance and refurbishment in domestic housing sector for utilising BIM processes.	
	(García Kerdan <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	The paper describes a systematic framework that uses exergoeconomic theory integrated into 'building energy retrofit' (BER) design.	
	(Marasco and Kontokosta, 2016)	This paper explores the ways to utilize available data to target ECMs across a city's entire building stock	
	(Munarim and Ghisi, 2016)	The paper proposes a prospect of environmental indicators to evaluate the feasibility of architectural rehabilitation	
	(Bomberg, Gibson and Zhang, 2015)	This article highlights the need for an active role for building physics in the development of near-zero energy buildings.	
	(De Lieto Vollaro <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	The paper examines computerized procedures to calculate in an accurate way the annual energy demand taking in consideration the inertial properties of the structure	
	(Dineen, Rogan and Ó Gallachóir, 2015)	This paper presents a novel bottom up approach to modelling the energy savings potential of energy efficiency improvement measures.	
	(Hsu, 2015)	This paper identifies several interactions between technical and non-technical parameters for further analysis, policy development and targeting Data	
	(Fawcett and Killip, 2014)	This paper shows an alternative model of low carbon retrofit whereby improvements happen step by step over several years.	
	(Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	This paper evaluates the building integrated energy efficiency taking into account the economic and energy efficiency of building envelope and cooling and heating resource	
	(de Wilde and Tian, 2012)	This paper reports on the use of building performance simulation to quantify the risks that climate change poses to the thermal performance of buildings, and to their critical functions.	
	(Heo, Choudhary and Augenbroe, 2012)	This paper presents a scalable, probabilistic methodology that can support large scale investments in energy retrofit of buildings while accounting for uncertainty.	
(Lawrence <i>et al.</i> , 2012)	This paper introduces the concept of Facilities Management and Modeling as a new form of information systems to apply the principles of Energy Informatics to increasing energy efficiency in building operations.		
Occupant behaviour modelling	(Mohareb <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	This paper investigates on retrofit measures taking into account how to balance energy and comfort needs.	Occupant Data Behaviour
	(Roberti <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	This paper presents a methodology that permits finding and comparing optimal retrofits for historic buildings in a trans-disciplinary and quantitative way.	
	(Parker <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	This paper describes a protocol for extracting and using freely available metadata to create occupancy schedules that are used as inputs for dynamic simulation models.	
	(Gupta and Gregg, 2016)	This paper uses a socio-technical building performance evaluation approach to assess the pre- and post- actual performance of two discrete deep low energy retrofits.	
	(Hong <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	This paper introduced the most recent advances and current obstacles in modelling occupant behaviour and quantifying its impact on building energy use.	
(Terés-Zubiaga <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	This paper investigates on the occupants' behaviour and the rebound effect, which show significant differences on energy consumption values.		

Life Cycle Analysis Modelling	(Yan <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	This paper outlines the obstacles and future needs and directions of occupant behaviour modelling.	Assessment Forecast Performance
	(Rhodes <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	This paper examines how energy efficiency retrofits and operational changes can influence a building's total and temporal energy use.	
	(Tianzhen Hong <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	This paper proposes a new holistic approach powered by building performance data and analytics.	
	(Chuah, Raghunathan and Jha, 2013)	This paper proposes retrofit modules with which the user can quickly and easily generate building models to perform retrofit comparison simulations.	
	(Neto and Fiorelli, 2008)	This paper proposes a comparison between a simple model based on artificial neural network and a model that is based on physical principles.	
	(Yalcintas, 2008)	This paper proposes a model that estimates energy savings from retrofit projects. A comparison between before and after the retrofits was used to develop the method.	
	(Bazjanac, 2004)	This paper seeks to increase the quality of building energy simulation through simultaneous interaction of multiple design and simulation tools.	
	(Fedoruk <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	This paper investigates on the 'performance gap' between designed and actual energy performance of buildings taking into account different stages of a building life cycle.	
	(Beccali <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	This paper studies the strong interplay among all the phases of a building life-cycle.	
	(Peuportier, Thiers and Guiavarch, 2013)	This paper focuses on the implications of life cycle assessment in thermal analysis.	
(Ardente <i>et al.</i> , 2011)	This paper highlights the role of the life cycle approach for selecting the most effective options during the design and implementation of retrofit actions.		
(Dong, Kennedy and Pressnail, 2005)	This paper compares demolishing and rebuilding action from the life cycle environmental and economic analyses point of view.		

Table 3 Information modelling process category and lines of research

Category: ER and decision-making process – main concept: OPTIMIZATION

Line of Research	References	Trans-disciplinary scope detected:	Key Concepts
Multi-attribute information	(Ascione, Bianco, De Masi, <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	This paper applies a multi-objective approach to find robust cost-optimal energy retrofit solutions and to assess their resilience to global warming.	Financial Cost Mechanism
	(Ascione, Bianco, De Stasio, <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	This paper investigates on how to predict building energy performance with low computational times and good reliability.	
	(Broderick <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	This paper highlights the importance of characterising indoor air quality post energy retrofits within the overall building energy performance.	
	(Tadeu <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	This paper considers a multi-objective optimization approach to identify the minimum global cost and primary energy needs	
	(Tariku, Kumaran and Fazio, 2015)	This paper examines a whole-building hygro-thermal model, which is used for evaluation of various retrofit design parameters	
	(Shao, Geyer and Lang, 2014)	This paper establishes a model-based method to support design teams in making informed multi-criteria decisions for energy-efficiency solutions	
	(Taehoon Hong <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	This paper aimed to develop a decision support model for establishing the optimal energy retrofit strategy.	
	(Xu, Taylor and Pisello, 2014)	This paper investigates on energy saving potential as results of a network synergy effect.	
	(Kumbaroğlu and Madlener, 2012)	This paper explores a techno-economic evaluation method for the energy retrofit of buildings.	
	(Kanapeckiene <i>et al.</i> , 2011)	This paper develops a Multi-Attribute Decision-Making methods in order to prioritize the alternatives of comparative projects quite accurately	
(Diakaki <i>et al.</i> , 2010)	This paper explores a methodology to define a optimal solution taking into account multiple and usually competitive objectives		
(Diakaki, Grigoroudis and	This paper investigates the feasibility of multi-objective optimization techniques to the problem of the improvement of the energy efficiency in buildings.		

Bottom-up methodolog	Kolokotsa, 2008)		Criteria Incentive Inhabitant
	(Yushchenko and Patel, 2017)	The paper reviews the existing practices of cost-effectiveness analysis and propose a modified methodology that allows considering perspectives of different stakeholders	
	(Vilches, Barrios Padura and Molina Huelva, 2017)	This paper introduces a methodology to choose the most appropriate retrofit measure in a context of fuel poverty.	
	(Delmastro, Mutani and Corgnati, 2016)	This paper presents a new bottom-up methodology to aid decision-makers in the energy planning process	
	(Kontokosta, 2016)	This paper examines the effects of ownership type, tenant demand, and real estate market location on building energy retrofit decisions in the commercial office sector.	
	(Shen <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	This paper investigates on policy instrument as key to drive improving energy-efficiency in building sectors.	
	(Trencher <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	This paper examines ten programmes to advance energy efficiency and retrofitting of existing.	
	(Senel Solmaz, Halicioglu and Gunhan, 2016)	The study presents an optimization-based decision support approach to determine the optimal energy efficiency retrofit options in existing buildings.	
	(Mauro <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	This paper introduces a novel methodology aimed at supporting robust cost-optimal energy retrofit solutions for building categories.	
	(Yang, Ergan and Knox, 2015)	This paper provides findings on information requirements of integrated design teams when evaluating retrofit options in immersive virtual environments.	
Economic and socio-technical factors	(Vlasova and Gram-Hanssen, 2014)	This paper argues that the success of energy-focused retrofit projects is conditioned by their compatibility with the everyday practices of the families living	Economics Integration Investments
	(Asadi <i>et al.</i> , 2011)	This paper presents a multi-objective optimization model to assist stakeholders in the definition of ER intervention measures	
	(Kolokotsa <i>et al.</i> , 2009)	This paper analyses the decision support processes towards energy efficiency and improvement of the environmental quality in buildings.	
	(Ahmed <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	This paper introduces a systematic methodology to support the decision-making process for the integration of various improvement options	
	(Shakouri, Lee and Choi, 2015)	This paper describes a quantitative decision-support model for Community-based PV Investment Model	
	(Asadi <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	This paper presents a multi-objective optimization model using genetic algorithm and artificial neural network to quantitatively assess technology choices	
	(Ballarini, Corgnati and Corrado, 2014)	This article presents a methodology for the identification of reference buildings aimed at creating a harmonised structure for “European Building Typologies”	
	(Eriksson <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	This paper describes a heritage impact assessment methodology to enable such a balancing process in a well-structured and systematic way	

Table 4 Decision-making process category and lines of research

Category: ER and innovative technical solutions – main concept: THERMAL HEAT

Line of Research	References	Transdisciplinary scope detected:	Key Concept
Innovative building materials	(Tovarović and Ivanović-Šekularac, Jelena Šekularac, 2017)	This paper analyses thermal comfort of glass façade. Special attention was paid to the implementation of media technologies and final effects on energy balance	Properties Inertia Insulation
	(Berardi, 2016)	This paper focuses on the benefits on the local microclimate and the building energy saving resulting from green roof retrofits.	
	(Pérez-Urrestarazu, Luis Fernández-Cañero, Rafael Franco-Salas and Egea, 2016)	This paper investigates on vertical greening systems as structures that allow vegetation to spread over a building facade or interior wall.	
	(Aste <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	This paper analyses the importance of the dynamic thermal properties as one of the design parameters.	
	(Saber <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	This paper compares the steady-state and transient thermal performance of three	

		wall assemblies.		
	(Ascione <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	This paper examines a phase change materials integrated in the building exterior envelope.		
Passive, active and smart technologies	(Carlos, 2017)	This paper shows how passive air heating system can be improved in order to collect more solar heat.		
	(Eliopoulou and Mantziou, 2017)	This paper investigates on the relationships between basic architectural features and energy performance.		
	(Biyanto <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	The paper investigates on the performance of heat exchanger.		
	(Cuce, 2016)	The paper investigates on news PV glazing products.		
	(Evola and Margani, 2016)	This paper investigates the energy and economic profitability of renovating residential buildings through the integration of PV panels on facades.		
	(Hengstberger <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	This paper investigates on the thermal comfort in buildings with facade integrated solar thermal collectors.		
	(Si <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	This paper compares a selection of green technologies where multiple criteria exist and interrelate.		
	(Giovannardi <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	The paper proposes the concept and design of a modular unglazed solar thermal façade component for facilitating the installation of active solar façade		
	(Monetti, Fabrizio and Filippi, 2015)	This paper analyses the application of space heating control devices such as thermostatic radiators valves on an old existing multi-family building.	Bioclimatic Control Integrated	
	(Smith and Svendsen, 2015)	This paper shows an experiment application of a short plastic rotary heat exchanger.		
	(Capeluto and Ochoa, 2014)	This article presents a simplified methodology to identify preferred strategies and combinations for the early design stages of such system		
		(Moran <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	This paper demonstrates the use of the Passive House Planning Package modelling tool to assess the potential for retrofit adaptation measures.	
		(Häkkinen, 2012)	This paper explains the method for the analysis of refurbishment concepts.	
		(Halawa, 2009)	This paper discusses about bioclimatic concepts, principles and strategies for large-scale buildings for the purposes of advanced renovation.	
	(Hestnes and Kofoed, 2002)	The paper promotes passive solar and energy efficient retrofitting measures in office buildings.		
	(Santamouris and Dascalaki, 2002)	The paper presents global retrofitting strategies in order to promote successful and cost-effective implementation of passive solar measures.		
Renovation of building sector	(Carbonaro <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	The paper illustrates the results of a joint research project involving manufacturers and research centers, adopting an integrated multi-objective design process		
	(Thomsen <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	This paper focuses on the tenants' overall satisfaction with the retrofitting process and the results of the retrofitting.		
	(Li <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	This study analyses the economic and financial issues in deploying CO2 capture in the cement industry.		
	(Ochoa and Capeluto, 2015)	The paper presents a methodology with integrative approach between energy and economic aspects.	Prefabricated Industry Research	
	(Rovers, 2014)	The paper illustrates an application of standardized process in order to improve ER actions.		
	(Silva <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	This paper presents a new prefabricated retrofit module solution for the facades of existing buildings.		
	(Xing, Hewitt and Griffiths, 2011)	This paper categorises a range of technologies for building refurbishment in a sequential manner.		
	(Aouad, Ozorhon and Abbott, 2010)	This paper provides an insight for future innovation research activities and for the role of universities in working with industry to promote innovation		

Table 5. Innovative technical solutions category and lines of research

Category: ER and energy and environmental awareness – main concept: KNOWLEDGE

Line of Research	References	Trans-disciplinary scope detected:	Key Concept
Integrated Community energy system	(Süsser, Döring and Ratter, 2017)	This paper analyses, theoretically and empirically, the multifaceted interplay between place, local entrepreneurship and ‘community renewable energy’.	Local Entrepreneurship Decentralised
	(Koirala <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	This paper presents a model-based framework to assess the distributed energy resources-consumer adoption model.	
	(Peck and Parker, 2016)	This paper investigates on ‘Energy Concept’ in order to contribute understanding of how organisations may implement renewable energies and improve energy efficiency.	
	(Rydin <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	This paper analyses local energy initiatives identifying barriers, drivers and incentives to explain their emergence (or not).	
	(Gough, 2015)	This article examines the complementarity of liveability and sustainability at a theoretical level but recognizes that linkage in practice is complex	
	(Van Der Schoor and Scholtens, 2015)	This paper investigates on the transition towards renewable and sustainable energy focusing on what is happening at the local community level.	
	(Simpson <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	This paper studies the variation in operational performance due to the intervention sequence.	
	(Sauter and Watson, 2007)	This paper argues on social acceptance of renewable energy innovation	
Comfort and Quality of life	(Santangelo and Tondelli, 2017)	The paper examines the existing energy policy instruments and the current analysis methods in relation to occupant behaviour.	Social Policy Instruments
	(Berry <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	This paper investigates on the level of householders’ knowledge on smart technologies.	
	(Jenkins, 2010)	This paper focuses on the problem of installing non-cost effective measure.	
	(Walker, 2008)	This paper investigates on the meaning of “community-owned production and use“	
Socio-technological learning process	(Voytenko <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	This paper examines how the ULL concept is being operationalised in contemporary urban governance for sustainability and low carbon cities.	Education, Experiments Networks
	(Kersten <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	This paper explores methods to transfer technological knowledge among residents	
	(Petri <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	This paper presents a web-based platform solution that provides integrated access to sustainability resources in the form of interactive, user-oriented services	
	(Joss, Cowley and Tomozeiu, 2013)	This papers explores the ‘ubiquitous eco-city’ paradigm with strong local contextualisation and social sustainability measures	
	(Klemeš <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	This paper explores the development of methods and tools, multimedia internet-based teaching and learning programs for future practitioners.	
	Glad, 2012)	This paper uses a socio-technical approach, based on social learning theory in order to examine the energy system transition.	

Table 6. Energy and environmental awareness category and lines of research

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